

Immunofluorescence on 3D basolateral and apical-out enteroids to assess the polarity

Note1: for the reagents refer to “List of reagents for enteroid protocols” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13847508)

Note2: Refer to protocol “Generation of enteroids from fresh porcine jejunum” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13848853)

Note3: Refer to protocol “Generation of apical-out enteroids” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13849682)

Note4: Use at least 100 basolateral enteroids, generated in 3D Geltrex™ culture and 200 apical-out enteroids. For each step of this protocol, pellet enteroids at 300 g for 1’.

- 1) Fix enteroid pellet with 300 μ L 4% paraformaldehyde/PBS for 30’ at RT
- 2) Remove the fixative and wash twice in PBSL
- 3) Incubate the pellet with 500 μ L 3D Permeabilization/blocking Buffer (3D P/BB) for 3h at RT
- 4) Incubate the pellet with anti ZO-1 primary antibody in 3D P/BB, overnight at 4°C
- 5) Wash 3 times for 10’ in WB, on a rocking platform
- 6) Incubate the pellet with the secondary antibody diluted in 3D P/BB for 4h at RT
- 7) Incubate the pellet in DAPI in PBSL for 30’ at RT
- 8) Wash 4 times for 10’ in PBSL, on a rocking platform
- 9) Resuspend the enteroids in a drop (40-50 μ L) of mounting medium and place them on a glass slide with concavities
- 10) Mount the coverslip and image using a confocal microscope